

FOODITY launches its first open call to fund data-driven solutions for food and nutrition

- The EU-funded project FOODITY will fund six data-driven solutions to boost innovation in food and nutrition while putting the power of personal data use back into the hands of citizens — enabling them to create healthier and more sustainable food systems.
- FOODITY's €1M pilot development programme beneficiaries will receive up to €187,500, as well as tailored mentoring and training, technical support, and business sustainability to advance their products and services over the course of 12 months.
- The organisations interested in participating in the programme can apply to the FOODITY Open Call #1 from 5 September to 8 November 2023 to get the support they need to develop their solutions and scale their impact.

The consortium of **FOODITY — F**ood and **nutritiOn Data-driven innovation respectful of citizen's Data SovereignTY** — is pleased to announce the launch of its first open call as part of the development of a dynamic **ecosystem of digital solutions for food and nutrition** that respects citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty in Europe.

Through its **Open Call #1**, FOODITY will support six disruptive digital solutions for food and nutrition. These will allow citizens complete control over their personal data, empowering them to make better — more environmentally friendly and healthier — dietary choices, thus contributing to **better food systems** and **climate change mitigation**.

The selected pilot project proposals will provide novel solutions to existing research and technical challenges to achieve the **Food 2030**¹ (the EU's research and innovation policy to build better food systems by 2030) key priorities: Food systems supporting a healthy planet, Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, Circularity and resource efficiency, and Innovation and empowering communities.

¹ [Food 2030: Research and innovation policy to make our food systems ready for the future.](#)

The Open Call will focus on three key areas — personalised food and nutrition, sustainable food systems, and shopping experiences — and one open challenge.

What's in it for you?

The FOODITY value-added services

The FOODITY Open Call beneficiaries — FOODITY innovators — will access a wide range of added-value services, from **financial support** (up to **€187.500** per beneficiary) to expert **mentoring and training, group coaching and technical support** to use the infrastructure and core components of the programme.

At the end of the programme, the FOODITY innovators will carry out an **Impact Assessment** of the results obtained by their pilots regarding the perception of end-users' control over their personal data. They will also receive support by connecting them to different ways of **sustainability**, ranging from VCs to training on equity-free funding.

Who are we looking for?

The FOODITY innovators

FOODITY is looking for organisations with both **technical and social innovation** expertise as well as **citizen engagement** knowledge to develop pilot projects.

- Small or Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) and startups
- Social Innovation Actors (SIAs)
- Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) and universities
- Training organisations

“Our open call is targeting multidisciplinary teams to develop solutions that will give citizens control over their data and where this data can have a strong societal impact, particularly in the food and nutrition domains. We also require social innovation and citizen engagement activities in their proposals. These are two important pillars to boost the impact of the solutions we will support.” Samuel Almeida, FOODITY Project Coordinator.

The FOODITY Open Call #1 is open from 5 September to 8 November 2023 (17:00 CET).

Do not miss the chance to apply and be part of the food innovation revolution!

For more information about the project and the open call, visit the [**FOODITY website**](#).

About FOODITY

In total, FOODITY will invest €2M in its pilot development programme to fund 12 solutions demonstrating the potential of data-driven innovation in food and nutrition while boosting citizen data sovereignty.

FOODITY is an ambitious impact-driven project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe programme. Over 3 years (2023 – 2026), the FOODITY team, comprised of 7 partners from 7 countries, will work to revolutionise European food and nutrition systems.

From top-level experts in ICT-based solutions for the food and nutrition sector (CERTH), technologies for user's control of personal data (JIBE) and integration of data commons into federated infrastructure (SOFTEAM) to experienced professionals in engaging citizens (F6S, AUSTRALO and SPLORO) and social innovation (ZSI):

Learn more about **FOODITY** and contact us at opencalls@foodity.eu for more information about our open calls.

For marketing and press purposes, please get in touch with raquel@australo.org.

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